

Decentring the Study of Migrant
Returns and Return Policies

Return Migration Infrastructures – Poland and Georgia

WP3 Country Dossier

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List of Abbreviations

AVR	assisted voluntary return
CMR	Centre of Migration Research of the University of Warsaw
Dz.U.	Journal of Laws of the Republic of Poland (in Polish: <i>Dziennik Ustaw Rzeczypospolitej Polskiej</i>)
ECtHR	European Court of Human Rights
EU	European Union
EURODAC	European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database
Frontex	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
ICMPD	International Centre for Migration Policy Development
IGOs	intergovernmental organisations
IOM	International Organisation for Migration
KSIP	National Police Information System (in Polish: <i>Krajowy System Informacyjny Policji</i>)
NGOs	non-governmental organisations
OFII	French Office for Immigration and Integration
PiS	the Law and Justice party (in Polish: <i>Prawo i Sprawiedliwość</i>)
RCMES	Readmission Case Management Electronic System
RMI	Return Migration Infrastructures
SCMI	State Commission on Migration Issues
SEP	Stakeholder Expert Panel
SIS	Schengen Information System
UNHCR	Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VIS	Visa Information System
WP	Work Package
ZUS	Poland's Social Insurance Institution (in Polish: <i>Zakład Ubezpieczeń Społecznych</i>)

Summary

This Poland-Georgia country dossier is part of Work Package 3 (WP3) of the GAPs project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is put into practice through the concept of ‘Return Migration Infrastructures’ (RMI) by focusing on the so-called ‘crucial meso-level’ (Faist 2010). Following from the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g., Xiang and Lindquist 2014), the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (‘doings’), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape—i.e., facilitate or undermine and contest—the daily operation of returns. In doing so, it explores how the aforementioned components work together on multiple scales and create messy realities on the ground because of various practices (Koinova et al. 2021).

In this report we present three types of returns—assisted voluntary returns, forced removals, and pushbacks. However, we explore mostly forced removals, which is a broad category of returns being in the middle of the continuum of coercion between assisted voluntary returns and pushbacks. Pushbacks are an object of interest of an emerging body of scholarship on the crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border. At the same time, the ‘standard’ return procedures remain under-researched, and this report aims to address this gap. This report mainly focuses on Poland, an EU member state that is considered a country sending foreign returnees, mostly to their countries of origin outside the EU. An important characteristic of Poland is that its eastern border is part of the EU’s (and Schengen area’s) external border. Poland borders three non-EU countries: Russia (Kaliningrad region), Belarus, and Ukraine. The land border with Ukraine is the longest of these. Another country we take into account in selected aspects is Georgia, a non-EU country, one of the countries targeted by the EU Eastern Partnership initiative, and a country receiving a significant number of its nationals returned from the EU. We pay particular attention to the returns of Georgian citizens from Poland (with various levels of coercion), as they represent one of the largest groups of returned foreigners under Poland’s return practices. In the case of Georgia, we treated its RMI as the extension of Poland’s RMI, with a strong focus on how Georgian nationals are received in their home country and what they are offered after return, especially within the reintegration scheme.

Three types of returns presented in this report—assisted voluntary returns, forced removals, and pushbacks—should not be seen as strictly separate forms of border practices targeting migrants in Poland. Instead, they occupy different points on a continuum of coercion regarding the construction of return. A given person, e.g., one entering Poland irregularly from Belarus with the will to apply for international protection, may be either pushed back or issued a removal order. If the application was lodged but ended with negative decision, the person may leave voluntarily or forcibly. Thus, each form can happen to the same person and many contingent factors can impact how the return is processed. These factors concern the practices of various actors and their capabilities stemming from accessible materials. Moreover, as the practices (doings) are based in legal acts, they also vary depending on the interplay of actors engaged, their power and interests. The presented construction of return should be understood in the context of Poland’s position in the global migration system. The cooperation of Georgia and the EU in terms of returns is an example of the externalisation of migration policies by the EU. It is substantially facilitated by the previous commitment of Georgians to European integration but also by the extensive network of local non-governmental organisations implementing reintegration schemes. However, despite the relevance of Georgia as a country receiving returnees from Poland, there are currently no bilateral programmes enhancing return procedures developed by Polish authorities.

Keywords: Poland, Georgia, Return Migration Infrastructures, assisted voluntary return, forced removal, pushback, reintegration

The GAPs project

GAPs is a Horizon Europe project that aims to conduct a comprehensive multidisciplinary study of the drivers of return policies and the barriers to and enablers of international cooperation on return migration. The overall aim of the project is to examine the disconnects and discrepancies between the expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes by decentring the dominant, one-sided understanding of ‘return policymaking’. To this end, GAPs:

- examines the shortcomings of the EU’s return governance,
- analyses enablers of and barriers to international cooperation, and,
- explores the perspectives of migrants themselves to understand their knowledge, aspirations and experiences with return policies.

GAPs combines its approach with three innovative concepts:

- a focus on return migration infrastructures (RMI), which allows the project to analyse governance gaps;
- an analysis of return migration diplomacy to understand how relations between EU member states and with third countries hinder cooperation on return; and,
- a trajectory approach, which uses a socio-spatial and temporal lens to understand migrant agency.

GAPs is a three-year interdisciplinary research project (2023–2026), coordinated by Uppsala University and the Bonn International Centre for Conflict Studies (BICC) with 17 partners in 12 countries on four continents. GAPs’ fieldwork was conducted in 12 countries: Sweden, Nigeria, Germany, Morocco, the Netherlands, Afghanistan, Poland, Georgia, Turkey, Tunisia, Greece, and Iraq.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Brief introduction of the wider GAPs project and WP3

Return migration has become a policy priority worldwide, especially in Europe. The GAPs project is a Horizon Europe project (2023–2026) that investigates the drivers of return policies and the potential disconnects between the expectations of return policies and their actual outcomes on the ground. It follows a decentring approach to migration governance and seeks to move beyond a Euro-centric understanding of return policymaking. The consortium consists of 17 partners in 12 countries across four different continents¹. This Poland-Georgia country dossier is part of Work Package 3 (WP3) of the GAPs project. This work package aims to study how return migration governance is put into practice through the concept of ‘Return Migration Infrastructures’ (RMI) by focusing on the so-called ‘crucial meso-level’ (Faist 2010). Following from the infrastructural turn in migration studies (e.g., Xiang and Lindquist 2014), the aim is to understand the relations and interactions between a wide variety of actors and their roles, their practices (‘doings’), as well as the materialities and technologies that together shape—i.e., facilitate or undermine and contest—the daily operation of returns. In doing so, it explores how the aforementioned components work together on multiple scales and create messy realities on the ground because of various practices (Koinova et al. 2021).

Moreover, WP3 investigates an axis of coercion that includes three types of RMI, namely assisted returns, forced removals, and pushbacks, by going beyond simplistic binaries of voluntariness versus forced returns (Sahin-Mencutek and Triandafyllidou 2024). WP3 research was implemented both in selected EU countries (particularly in Germany, Greece, the Netherlands, Poland, and Sweden) and in third countries (including Georgia, Iraq, Morocco, Nigeria, Tunisia, and Turkey). EU partner countries focus on RMI returning people either to one member state from another in the case of Dublin rules, or to non-EU states, and non-EU partners focus on RMI receiving returnees from the EU.

1.2. Introduction of the case study

In this report we present three types of returns—assisted voluntary returns, forced removals, and pushbacks. However, we explore mostly forced removals, which is a broad category of returns being in the middle of the continuum of coercion between assisted voluntary returns and pushbacks. Pushbacks are an object of interest of an emerging body of scholarship on the crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border. At the same time, the ‘standard’ return procedures remain under-researched, and this report aims to address this gap.

Forced returns are understood as the execution of removal orders. In this report, the term ‘removal order’ is used for the decision obliging a person to return to another state (in Polish: *decyzja o zobowiązaniu do powrotu*) issued by the commander responsible for the Border Guard post or unit. The reasons for issuance of the decision obliging a person to return are broad and can vary from an irregular stay or a stay for a purpose inconsistent with the declared one². They are also a consequence of refusals in asylum³ or labour permit cases. Thus, the removal order remains the final stage of the complex phenomena regulating migrants’ presence on Poland’s territory. Therefore, in this report, we analyse how deportability is being constructed, with particular attention to the latest stage, i.e., the issuance and execution of the removal order. However, it should be remembered that returns carried out by the Border

¹ For more information, see: <https://www.returnmigration.eu/about>.

² Art. 302 of the Act on foreigners, and see (Trylińska et al. 2024).

³ The term ‘asylum’ is used in this report to depict all forms of protection except temporary protection. In Polish law, ‘asylum’ remains a separate category of national protection, rarely applied and different from refugee status and subsidiary protection.

Guard are only an element of the whole migration policy, which is designed by the Ministry of the Interior and Administration and applied by various actors.

The analysis of forced removals will be divided into subsections devoted to actors, doings, materials, and relations. The aim of this analysis is to present how different stakeholders cooperate with each other, within what kind of procedures, what kind of material and IT infrastructure, and, last but not least, what tensions this cooperation provokes. The data presented in this report can serve further research on the production of deportability of migrants in Poland, together with the data obtained within WP7, which focuses on migrants' trajectories⁴.

2. Methods

2.1. General methodological framework of WP3

The WP3 research was planned between June 2023 and June 2024, comprising two main tasks. The first was to create an overview of the RMI in each partner country encapsulated in a form of flow maps based on desk research. Desk research included the study of reports, policy briefs, informative leaflets, data reports, newsletters, websites, etc., on implementing returns from involved actors and/or observers, following the study of the legal framework on return migration (based on WP2⁵). Desk research and the flow maps produced are structured around 1) the actors involved, 2) their doings, and 3) the materials and technologies used. Second, the WP3 research focused on selecting a particular RMI type (assisted returns, forced removal, or pushbacks) as a case study. The assumption was to start the empirical part of the research from a specific 'entry point' on the ground related to the everyday workings of the RMI selected. The most significant component of WP3 research activities was semi-structured interviews in the countries under study with meso-level actors involved in the everyday operation of the return procedure that may facilitate and contest return operations. Partners were also encouraged to conduct ethnographic observations during the interviews or on other suitable occasions on a voluntary basis.

2.2. Methodological framework for the Poland and Georgia cases

This report mainly focuses on Poland, an EU member state that is considered a country sending foreign returnees, mostly to their countries of origin outside the EU. An important characteristic of Poland is that its eastern border is part of the EU's (and Schengen area's) external border. Poland borders three non-EU countries: Russia (Kaliningrad region), Belarus, and Ukraine. The land border with Ukraine is the longest of these.

Another country we take into account in selected aspects is Georgia, a non-EU country, one of the countries targeted by the EU Eastern Partnership initiative, and a country receiving a significant number of its nationals returned from the EU. We pay particular attention to the returns of Georgian citizens from Poland (with various levels of coercion), as they represent one of the largest groups of returned foreigners under Poland's return practices. At the same time, Georgia remains a country strongly committed to integration with EU structures.

This section discusses the strategies applied for gathering data (documents, literature, interviews, and other sources) and analysing the collected material, especially for Poland. It also mentions the limitations encountered. The methodology applied is compliant with the GAPs project guidelines for WP3, focused on RMI. Two different methodological approaches were used in this report. The first was legal and

⁴ See more: (Krępa et al. 2025).

⁵ See more: (Trylińska et al. 2024; Krępa et al. 2024).

policy analysis (desk research). It relied on an analysis of the legal, institutional, and infrastructure framework of the country's return procedures for foreigners covering 2015–2024. Along with official documents and statements, considering both the macro- and meso-levels, the reports and works published by international intergovernmental organisations (IGOs) and non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and academic literature were used. Statistics, legal documents, and information made available to the research team by Poland's Border Guard and the Office for Foreigners were an important addition to the research material. The second approach is heavily based on the qualitative research material collected from individual, in-depth, semi-structured meso-level interviews conducted within the project. In this report, the meso-level perspective was included in selected sections, which allows for a smooth and consistent presentation and discussion of various topics concerning return policy, showing the respondents' approach. In our qualitative research, the selection of meso-level respondents was purposeful. The goal was to obtain opinions on the qualitative aspects of the functioning of return policy in Poland, including both law and practice. Due to the sample's non-exhaustive nature, the presented qualitative research results cannot be generalised, but they illustrate some trends and examples in the field.

For meso-level interviews, it was crucial to identify sampling criteria for Poland, keeping in mind the general guidelines developed within the GAPs consortium. National specificity was also taken into account. From April to August 2024, we conducted a total of 20 individual in-depth semi-structured interviews with representatives of public administration, international organisations, social organisations, and other experts and meso-level practitioners with knowledge and expertise regarding the return migration and return policy in this country. When recruiting respondents, we focused on those with experience corresponding to meso-level activities within RMI. The final interview sample for Poland included, e.g., international and national officials, border guards, lawyers, psychologists, interpreters, and NGO employees.

The interviews were conducted using the GAPs WP3 interview guidelines, adapted to the country context and university requirements, and were preceded by obtaining clearance from the Ethics Committee of the Centre of Migration Research at the University of Warsaw. The principles of informed consent and anonymous participation were crucial for the research team when conducting the interviews. The respondents were informed about the project's scope and aim of the research activities. Depending on the respondent, we obtained his/her written and/or oral consent to participate in the study. This applies to interviewees from both Poland and Georgia.

In the case of Georgia, we treated its RMI as the extension of Poland's RMI, with a strong focus on how Georgian nationals are received in their home country and what they are offered after return, especially within the reintegration scheme. Similar to the case of Poland, our desk research included the collection and analysis of some national legal and policy documents and websites (mostly those available in English), as well as websites, reports, and materials of IGOs and NGOs operating in Georgia, supplemented with academic literature. Primary data were obtained thanks to fieldwork regarding Georgia from February to May 2024, mostly within a short research stay of two project team members in Tbilisi. It allowed us to conduct most of our meso-level interviews and ethnographic observations, e.g., during the flight from Warsaw to Tbilisi and then during the stay in the capital city. Some interviews regarding the Georgian case were conducted in Poland, mainly online. We conducted individual in-depth interviews (in English, Russian, and Polish) with 25 representatives of international organisations, public institutions (including ministries), non-governmental organisations, and other experts (also Polish nationals specialising in the Southern Caucasus) who had required knowledge about returns to Georgia and the reintegration of Georgian citizens. The selection of meso-level respondents was purposeful, and in some cases, the snowballing recruitment technique was necessary. Access to some institutions and

respondents, especially in Tbilisi, would not be possible without the support of ‘gatekeepers’ we know. In addition, on the occasion of some on-site interviews, more than one representative per institution/organisation participated to provide complementary knowledge and expertise from specific policy areas. These respondents are counted separately, which is reflected in the codes of the specific interviews. In addition, some detailed information regarding law, policy, and statistics about returns and reintegration was received upon request, e.g., from ministries.

The analysis conducted for this report has a qualitative character and was supported by Dedoose software. To conduct the analysis, the common coding scheme for WP3 was used, making some country-specific revisions and additions.

Our research material was enriched by the discussions in two hybrid meetings (at the CMR premises and by Zoom) of the GAPs Stakeholder Expert Panel (SEP) in Poland, two organised in 2024 on 17 January and 29 November. It was transcribed and coded manually. SEP Poland comprises more than 20 experts who are currently representatives or formerly associated with international organisations, the national public administration, civil society organisations working for human rights (in particular, the rights of foreigners), academic and research institutions, research networks, think tanks, and lawyers-practitioners.

In addition, the Polish team members, including the co-authors of this report as of late 2024, were participants as speakers, experts, or audience members of several thematic events (conferences, workshops, seminars, and debates) in Poland and abroad dedicated to migration, asylum, and return issues. This allowed for numerous interactions and discussions with other experts in the field, as well as observations and access to additional materials.

The project team members’ past and current professional experience—including expertise in working in international organisations based in Europe, public administration institutions responsible for migration and asylum in Poland, and NGOs providing legal support and services to foreigners in Poland—was key to implementing research activities within WP3. This allowed for, among other things, in-depth insight into the monitoring of selected return operations from Poland, visits in the guarded centres for foreigners run by the Border Guard, as well as active involvement as lawyers-practitioners in the cases of foreigners under return, which unintentionally served as ethnographic studies.

Fieldwork in Georgia was planned before that in Poland. Poland held parliamentary elections in October 2023, in which a coalition of democratic parties won. A new government was not successfully formed until December 2023. After eight years, it replaced the right-wing coalition government of the Law and Justice (PiS) party. This led to changes in key positions in the Ministry of the Interior and Administration and the Border Guard. Only after the political and institutional situation in Poland had stabilised could the GAPs UW team launch efforts to start field research at the planned entry point, one of the detention centres managed by the Border Guard (in legal acts, called ‘guarded centres for foreigners’). Due to the long wait for a response and consent from the Border Guard’s side, the team started to carry out the remaining planned meso-level interviews in order not to delay the research. Finally, the Border Guard agreed to address our interview questions in writing (we count it as qualitative interview material, as they followed the interview scenario). Their justification for this format was a combination of reasons, such as a shortage of staff, volume of everyday work, and the need to collect contributions from various units and staff due to the complex scope of our questions. They provided rich and extensive comments.

3. Context

3.1. Context of migration⁶

Poland's migration system changed considerably alongside the country's transition from state socialism to capitalism and liberal democracy after 1989. However, until 2014, Poland was predominantly characterised by the net emigration of its citizens, especially after joining the EU in 2004 and Schengen zone in 2007. After that time, rapid economic growth, followed by the liberalisation of labour migration policy, triggered the evolution from a typical emigration country to an emigration-immigration one, with the prevalence of short-term Ukrainian economic migration (Górny et al. 2010; Górny et al. 2018; Okólski, Wach 2020; Strzelecki, Pachocka 2020). A further turn was caused by the outbreak of conflict in eastern Ukraine in 2014, resulting in the growing migration of Ukrainians abroad. Two years later, a positive migration balance in Poland was recorded for the first time since the post-1989 transformation (Okólski 2021; Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2022). The COVID-19 pandemic—despite numerous and frequently changing mobility restrictions—did not cause a sudden outflow of economic migrants from Poland (Jaroszewicz, Krępa, Pachocka 2024). As a result, according to Poland's Social Insurance Institution (ZUS), in March 2024, foreigners constituted almost 7% (1.138 million) of the labour force in the country (Polski Instytut Ekonomiczny 2024).

Asylum-seeking remains rather marginal in Poland compared to labour migration (see Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2022). The average recognition rate of asylum applications until 2020 was very low (about 17%), which considerably strengthens the need for an effective return policy. Another important development reinforcing this need is Belarus's instrumentalisation of migration, which has led to numerous irregular border crossings from this country to Poland (mostly by citizens of Middle Eastern and African countries) since August 2021 (see Krępa et al. 2025).

3.2. Historical overview of the social, economic, and political conditions of the development of RMI in Poland⁷

In the early 1990s, Poland joined the international system of human rights protection, which also applies to the issue of return migration: the Geneva Convention relating to the Status of Refugees of 1951, the Council of Europe (in both cases, it was 1991), and the Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms of 1950 (in 1993) (Sobczak-Szelc et al. 2022, pp. 20-40). Other important changes were linked to the accession to the EU; however, according to some scholars, this process was rather superficial, forced by the need to adapt national law to EU requirements, and not based on experience or values (Łazor 2016). In any case, adopting both the international and the EU-based legal framework was a crucial political factor shaping the emergence of the return system in post-transition Poland.

Until the migration-management crisis of 2015 (Pachocka, Caballero Vélez 2025), migration policy occupied a rather marginal position compared to other public policies in Poland. Between 1990 and 2015, Poland was primarily an emigration country, and immigration was mainly dealt with technocratically and administratively (Matyja, Siewierska-Chmaj, Pędziwiatr 2015; Adamczyk 2021). Return policy was not in the spotlight, and even some efforts were made to decrease the need to apply returns, like three amnesties allowing migrants to regularise their status.

⁶ For more details, see Section 2. Political Context (Trylińska et al. 2024, pp. 15-16).

⁷ Ibidem.

Since 2015, migration has remained a highly securitised topic in Poland (Adamczyk 2017), strengthening the urge to apply returns effectively. The government formed by the Law and Justice party in 2015-2023 based its rhetoric on anti-immigrant sentiment (Fomina, Kucharczyk 2018; Górak-Sosnowska, Pachocka 2019; Klaus 2020). In 2016, the PiS government abolished the previous government's migration-policy strategy, which had been adopted in 2012. It also refused to participate in the EU temporary relocation scheme from Italy and Greece, which provoked a clash with the EU institutions (Pachocka 2016; Pachocka, Caballero-Vélez 2025). The anti-immigrant policy was applied in the case of providing protection to foreigners in the territory of Poland, with reported refusals of access to asylum at the border crossing with Belarus at Terespol⁸ shortly after PiS took power in 2015 (Szczepanik 2018) while the approach to labour migration remained rather liberal. The situation related to asylum was exacerbated in 2021 when Belarusian leader Alexandr Lukashenko instrumentalised migration, mostly from the Middle East and Africa, to facilitate or even force irregular border crossings to Poland, Latvia, and Lithuania. This resulted in the militarisation of the border, construction of a steel fence, and pushbacks (Krępa, Fernández de la Reguera 2024). Despite the pushbacks, however, some international protection applications were allowed to be lodged, and after rejection thereof, the need for performing returns increased considerably. Importantly, the change of government in autumn 2023 has not significantly altered the situation so far (Bronitskaya et al 2024; WAM 2024a; 2024b). On the other hand, according to data from the Border Guard, in 2023 the number of asylum applicants lodged in Poland was 8,843, while in 2024 it was 15,197 (Border Guard n.d.). Moreover, the treatment of migrants on the border with Belarus vividly contrasted with the policy towards Ukrainians displaced due to the Russian aggression in the first months of the mass displacement (Bloch 2023).

The situation regarding labour migration was different. Due to significant labour market shortages and pressure from employers, the migration policy of PiS was shaped rather by economic logic and remained liberal despite the securitisation within the border and asylum regimes (Jaroszewicz, Krępa, Pachocka 2024). Moreover, most of the labour migrants come from countries which were not the object of securitisation in the Polish discourse on migration, predominantly Ukraine (Jaroszewicz, Grzymski 2021).

Another important development shaping the migration system in Poland was the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine in early 2022. Poland applied a solution based on temporary protection⁹, following the EU Temporary Protection Directive, and the general policy towards people fleeing the war was rather open-door based (Jaroszewicz, Grzymski, Krępa 2022). However, in case of the war's end, the question of the further stay of Ukrainian beneficiaries with temporary protection in Poland would become an essential issue regarding return policy.

An important element of the return migration context is crime involving foreigners in Poland. According to data obtained from the Police, there is a significant disproportion between different groups of migrants regarding committed crime. As the data show, the group particularly present in the criminal statistics are citizens of Georgia, especially in the categories of theft, burglary, and offences linked to driving. This could explain why Georgians have occupied the top position of returns from Poland since 2022.

⁸ In 2020, the European Court of Human Rights recognised this practice as a violation of the European Convention of Human Rights – see the case *M.K. AND OTHERS v. POLAND*: <https://hudoc.echr.coe.int/eng#%7B%22itemid%22:%5B%22001-207580%22%5D%7D>.

⁹ For Ukrainian citizens, a special law on temporary protection was created while for other nationals fleeing Ukraine Poland applied the 'standard' temporary protection stipulated already in law and launched according to the EU decision.

3.3. Return migration: trends and figures¹⁰

There is no constant trend regarding returns from Poland. The number of foreigners ordered to leave was growing each year since 2015 and in 2018 and 2019 exceeded 29,000 annually. Also, the biggest number of foreigners returning voluntarily (beneficiaries of voluntary return schemes) was observed in 2017 and 2018 (yet, the numbers are rather small, 507 and 450, respectively).

The main nationality of third-country nationals ordered to leave in 2015-2021 were Ukrainians. 2022 marked a change in this matter: Georgian nationals were ranked first, followed by Ukrainians and Iraqis (in 2021, Iraqis were second, which can be explained by the humanitarian crisis on the Polish-Belarusian border, ongoing since August 2021, within which Iraqis were a considerable group of foreigners entering Poland irregularly). In general, the main destinations of return are usually Poland's eastern neighbours and Georgia and Moldova.

While the number of Dublin returnees to Poland decreased considerably (from over 1,400 in 2016 and 2017 to less than 250 in the pandemic years 2020-21), the number of foreigners returned from Poland increased. However, the figures of Dublin transfers from Poland are much smaller: not exceeding 100 per year (with the exception of 2021).

The data on third-country unaccompanied minors returned following an order to leave are accessible only for the years 2022 and 2023, and during this period there was only one such case per year.

4. Return Migration Infrastructures in Poland

In this section, we present an overview of the return types on the two sides of the continuum of coercion. The so-called assisted voluntary returns are the procedures with the least level of coercion (however, there is a possibility as well that the decision to return through this procedure is not fully voluntary). On the other point of the continuum, there are pushbacks, which remain the most violent form of return. In the middle, there are 'standard' forced removals, which, due to their complexity, will be analysed more extensively in the next section.

4.1. Assisted return¹¹

Assisted returns are defined as 1) departures of migrants from the host country, 2) who formally comply/consent with their departure (even though there is often pressure to do so), and 3) receive a level of logistical, financial, administrative and / or interpersonal support in the process (Papatzani et al. forthcoming). The assistance is provided for those who decide to return voluntarily. There is no publicly accessible data on the number of foreigners for whom the Head of Office for Foreigners provided assisted voluntary return (AVR). The biggest number of foreigners who benefited from AVR from Poland between 2015 and 2023 were 507 and 450 people in 2017 and 2018, respectively (based on the Border Guard statistics we obtained upon request).

¹⁰ This section is partially developed on the basis of: (Trylińska et al. 2024, pp. 10-14). For more detailed statistics for Poland, see Section 1. Statistical Overview Regarding Returns and Readmissions at the National Level (Trylińska et al. 2024, pp. 10-14) and GAPs Data Repository on Return available at: <https://data.returnmigration.eu/>.

¹¹ This section was partially developed on the basis of: (Trylińska et al. 2024, pp. 10, 14, 23, 25, 39-40, 43, 47, 50, 54).

In Poland, if the foreigner declares an interest in voluntary return, the Commander-in-Chief of the Border Guard organises assistance in this regard. Assistance in voluntary return shall be granted upon the foreigner's application. The foreigner submits the application for assistance with voluntary return to the Commander-in-Chief of the Border Guard through indicated authorities: the commanding officer of the Border Guard division (Division Commander) or the commanding officer of the Border Guard post or the Head of the Office for Foreigners. In practice, this request is submitted directly to the International Organisation for Migration (IOM). The Act on foreigners provides the possibility of outsourcing the organisation's voluntary return scheme to another entity. Currently, the only entity of this kind is the IOM, which results from an agreement between the Minister of the Interior and Administration and the IOM of 12 July 2005. This agreement clearly defines the tasks of the minister, the IOM, and the mode of cooperation. The assistance includes medical care, travel costs, accommodation, and meals before the return. There is no information about the principle of family unity. Access to psychological care is limited. Foreigners placed in detention centres have access to a psychologist hired by the Border Guard (however, there was a problem with the access to psychological and medical assistance in some temporary detention centres opened in 2021 which are no longer functioning (NIK 2022)).

The decision on the obligation of the foreigner to return shall specify the period of voluntary departure, which shall be from 8 to 30 days, counted from the day of delivery of the decision. In some cases, however, the decision is immediately enforceable (if the foreigner is recognised as a security threat or there is a risk of absconding).

The Act on foreigners specifies who can benefit from assisted return (based on art. 334 of the Act on foreigners), to whom to apply and the deadline for submission of this application. Foreigners who are eligible to apply may receive multiple types of decisions, among others:

- a) a decision to oblige a foreigner to return with a deadline for voluntary departure,
- b) a decision to oblige a foreigner to return subject to compulsory execution of the order and who, due to the circumstances referred to in art. 400 of the Act on foreigners, has not been placed in a detention centre or in respect of whom an arrest for foreigners has not been applied or who has been released from a detention centre or an arrest for foreigners when it has been established that the circumstances referred to in art. 400 of the Act on foreigners apply, and in the case referred to in art. 406(1)(3) of the Act on foreigners,
- c) a foreigner who has been issued a decision to refuse refugee status or subsidiary protection or a decision to declare an application for international protection inadmissible,
- d) a foreigner who has been issued a decision to discontinue the procedures on granting international protection,
- e) a foreigner whose application for granting international protection was left without consideration for formal reasons,
- f) a foreigner staying on the territory of the Republic of Poland on the basis of a certificate referred to in art. 170 of the Act on foreigners (certificate confirming the presumption that the foreigner is a victim of trafficking in human beings) or on the basis of a temporary residence permit referred to in art. 176 of the Act on foreigners.

The Act on foreigners stipulates circumstances when the foreigner cannot voluntarily return (not specifying the deadline for voluntary departure). It applies to cases in which:

- 1) there is a risk of the foreigner's absconding or
- 2) this is required for reasons of national defence or state security or the protection of public security and public order.

The risk of absconding is established, taking into account whether the foreigner (art. 315(3). of the Act on foreigners):

- 1) has declared non-compliance with obligations arising from the receipt of a decision obliging a foreigner to return, or
- 2) does not possess any documents confirming his/her identity, or
- 3) has crossed or has attempted to cross the border illegally, or
- 4) entered the territory of the Republic of Poland during the period of validity of the entry in the list of foreigners whose stay in the territory of the Republic of Poland is undesirable, or in the Schengen Information System for the purpose of refusing entry and stay.

It should be noted that, in principle, the AVR does not include detention. However, it is possible to apply for this form of return while already being detained, e.g., within the asylum procedure.

A detailed flowchart of AVR in Poland is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Flowchart of assisted voluntary returns in Poland

Source: elaboration by Tomasz Sieniow with the support of Anna Trylińska; Ksenia Naranovich, visualisation.

4.2. Pushbacks¹²

Pushbacks are defined as states and supra-states practices of (1) moving migrants, who are – usually – at or near the border, away from their territories (2) by force and (3) before they officially enter that territory, which implies that they are obstructing access to the applicable legal and procedural frameworks of that territory (Papatzani et al. forthcoming). Pushbacks, officially named as ‘returning to the border line’, were introduced on the basis of regulations regarding the COVID-19 pandemic. The Ordinance of the Minister of the Interior and Administration of 13 March 2020¹³ introduced a catalogue of persons eligible to cross Polish borders (such as foreigners with a permit of stay or drivers of international transport). This act was amended on 21 August 2021¹⁴ and according to this law, persons discovered at these border crossings where border traffic has been suspended or restricted since March 2020 and even outside the territorial scope of the border crossing shall be returned to the state border line. This ‘return to the state border line’, as the Border Guard officially calls pushbacks, does not fall under the ‘standard’ return procedures based on the orders to leave the territory of the Republic of Poland (removal orders).

In 2021, Belarus started to issue visas to countries such as Iraq and Syria, facilitating irregular arrivals to the territory of the EU. The following year, the number of foreigners entering Belarus decreased while the number of those illegally crossing the border grew to 2,744. Independent reports show that the Polish border guards refused to accept international protection requests from those people and pushed them back to the Belarusian side multiple times (Bronitskaya et al. 2024). Parliament, on 14 October 2021, adopted amendments to the Act on foreigners, adding a provision to issue an administrative order to leave the territory of Poland to a person apprehended immediately after crossing the border contrary to the law.¹⁵ This statutory provision became a new legal basis for pushbacks.

As numerous reports by NGOs indicate, there is no clear way of differentiating the treatment of people who want to apply for asylum on the border with Belarus and, as a consequence, no clear way of deciding who is to be pushed back and who would be allowed to lodge an asylum application. Some applications are being accepted to be lodged. In 2024, the top three nationalities applying for asylum in Poland were those who rather did not cross the Polish-Belarusian border irregularly: Ukrainians, Belarusians, and Russians (over 70% of all applicants). However, there were also applicants from other countries, including Somalia and Eritrea (Office for Foreigners 2025). With much probability it can be said that these asylum-seekers lodged their applications after an irregular crossing of the border with Belarus (mostly in the forest area shortly after crossing, but also in other locations such as detention centres of on the way to other EU country).

The pushbacks are carried out by the Border Guard with the cooperation of the army, leading to, as already mentioned earlier, the militarisation of the border regime (Krępa, Fernández de la Reguera 2024) with a material barrier in the form of a steel fence with concertina wire, perimeter security, including thermovision. The military provides its staff with equipment, also in the form of vehicles. The main equipment for carrying out pushbacks are trucks, which serve to carry people, and the Border Guard posts, where migrants are often placed for a short time before deciding on pushback, as well as patrolling

¹² This section was partially developed on the basis of: (Trylińska et al. 2024, pp. 30-35).

¹³ Ordinance of the Minister of the Interior and Administration of 13 March 2020 on the temporary suspension or restriction of border traffic at specific border crossings, Dz.U. 2020, item 435.

¹⁴ Ordinance of The Minister of the Interior and Administration of 20 August 2021 amending the ordinance on the temporary suspension or restriction of border traffic at specific border crossings, Dz.U. 2021, item, 1536.

¹⁵ Act of 14 October 2021 amending the Act on foreigners and certain other acts, Dz.U. 2021, item 1918.

drones. The Border Guard transports migrants to the border fence, opens a gate and forces them to cross the border to Belarus.

As of the beginning of February 2025, the association We Are Monitoring reported more than 11,000 pushbacks on the border with Belarus and 89 deaths of migrants in this area (WAM n.d.). According to the NGOs defending human rights, the migrants experiencing pushbacks are often deprived of access not only to the asylum procedure but also to basic humanitarian and medical assistance (Bronitskaya et al. 2024; WAM 2024a; 2024b). The most difficult time is winter because in the east of Poland, the temperatures usually hover around 0 C° from the end of November till the beginning of March, with the possibility of a period of cold weather down to -20 C°. The NGOs provide humanitarian assistance in the form of food, clothes, powerbanks, and basic medical help. Some migrants are taken to local hospitals, but this does not guarantee that they will not be pushed back after their state of health improves.

The situation on the border is highly polarising in Polish society. Apart from NGOs and individual activists, some churches were engaged in providing assistance for migrants. On the other hand, there were far-right military groups attempting to ‘patrol’ the border area, however their activities were not supported by the state and eventually discontinued.

A flowchart of forced removals in Poland is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Flowchart of pushbacks in Poland

Source: elaboration by Tomasz Sieniow; Ksenia Naranovich, visualisation.

5. Detailed analysis of forced removals in Poland

In this section, we provide a closer look at how removal orders from Poland are carried out. Also, we analyse how this specific category of forced returns overlaps or transforms into other forms, such as assisted voluntary returns or pushbacks. Forced removals are defined as (1) the removal of migrants from a particular state after the arrival of the migrant in that state, (2) without migrant's consent, but (3) within the legal framework and procedures of the state (Papatzani et al. forthcoming). A flowchart of forced removals in Poland is presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Flowchart of forced removals in Poland

Source: elaboration by Tomasz Sieniow; Ksenia Naranovich, visualisation.

5.1. Actors involved in RMI in Poland and their roles

The leading institution in the management of returns in Poland is the Border Guard. The Commander-in-Chief of the Border Guard is the key state authority entitled to issue administrative decisions resulting in an obligation of the foreigner to leave the territory of Poland. At the same time, the Border Guard remains the competent authority for the implementation of the return policy, and in particular for actions related to organising voluntary and forced returns of third-country nationals to their country of origin.

In practice, the Border Guard cumulates almost overall power regarding both deciding and enforcing forced removals. It carries out controls over the legality of stay, which can result in issuing orders to leave Poland. It issues orders for both the first and the appeal instance. It decides whether to grant tolerated or humanitarian stay, which is the premise that makes the removal unenforceable. It maintains the material infrastructure necessary for the effectiveness of removals, and it carries out the removal operations. Finally, it decides whether to enforce an entry ban to the Schengen area, which is usually issued together with a removal order, and it can withdraw this ban upon request of the foreigner.

Among other important institutions are those that issue decisions resulting in the obligation to leave the country. These are of two categories. First, there are the regional representatives of the government (voivodes) who decide whether to grant permits of stay. Second, it is the Office for Foreigners, the appeal institution for stay permits and the first-instance institution regarding asylum decisions. Third, there is the Refugee Board, the appeal institution in the case of asylum.

At the same time, some actors control or often contest the forced return operations. The decisions issued by the Border Guard can be appealed to administrative courts and, if the appeal fails and there is a violation of the European Convention of Human Rights, to the European Court of Human Rights. The appeals are sometimes facilitated by the Commissioner for Human Rights (called also the Ombudsman) or the Commissioner for Children's Rights if the removal regards minors. The courts also decide on detention, which can be monitored by the Commissioners. Last but not least, various civil society institutions, such as NGOs, support foreigners in defending their rights, and some of them monitor the return operations. The Dialogue Foundation cooperates with the Border Guard in providing assistance for selected groups of migrants.

Another category is external actors, such as Frontex and institutions of countries of origin. Frontex can be considered a cooperating institution that facilitates some returns in the form of Joint Return Operations. In turn, countries of origin are crucial in making the return enforceable. They have to identify a person and issue him/her a travel document. The unwillingness of some countries to recognise and accept their citizens impacts the effectiveness of return operations. As one of the Border Guard officers told us: 'What is hampering [returns]? Well, first of all, as I said, documents entitling a foreigner to return, i.e., return documents, and the consent of the state to accept him' (IDI_PL_20).

Generally, our interviewees working for social organisations considered the Border Guard an actor determined to carry out removals. As one of the lawyers representing migrants observed:

It seems to me that if the Border Guard wants to implement the decision to oblige you to return, it will implement it, regardless of any violations that may or may not have occurred. From my experience I really know that it is very difficult to reverse this momentum to follow through on the decision to commit to returning once it happens (IDI_PL_1).

In turn, a Border Guard officer described his/her organisation as a 'machine which just follows the rules' (IDI_PL_20).

5.2. Implementation / 'doings' of forced removals in Poland

The forced removals can be considered a prerequisite for control over access to territory, and thus, they remain in logical connection to other elements of migration policy, such as visa policy and labour policy. Therefore, the initial point of the analysis of the implementation of forced returns is elucidating how deportability is produced.

Implementation of RMI depends on the categories of foreigners who face forced returns. The first category is people who did not possess any title of stay from the beginning of their presence in Poland. This is linked to the overall unwelcome policy towards some categories of migrants. As a lawyer working with foreigners told us, there is a group of countries from which the chances of obtaining a visa to Poland are 'minimal', such as Afghanistan, Yemen, or Iran (IDI_PL_1). As the human rights organisations report (WAM n.d.), these nationalities, together with other Middle Eastern ones, are broadly represented among people crossing the Polish-Belarusian border and attempting to apply for asylum in Poland; however, it is not possible to present a precise percentage of persons who lodge the application and those who face pushbacks. Importantly, it seems that pushbacks are the standard procedure for dealing with those who crossed the border from Belarus irregularly and were not allowed to lodge asylum applications. In turn, in the cases of migrants who irregularly enter other borders than the one with Belarus and are detained on Polish territory (rather a minority group among all forcibly returned) 'normal' forced removals are applied. Last but not least, forced returns regard people returned to Poland according to Dublin regulations (if the obligation to leave the country has already been issued in their case) and foreigners released from prisons.

Thus, the implementation of RMI pertains mainly to those migrants who entered Poland regularly but later on lost their title of stay, such as visa overstayers, refused asylum seekers, or people who lost their stay permit due to the completion of their labour contract and various difficulties with obtaining another one. In these cases, the precise application of return depends on the way the Border Guard obtains knowledge about the foreigner's lost title of stay. This knowledge could be obtained deliberately goes for inspections in order to collect the greatest possible harvest [sic]. And it is organised like a round-up instead of some planned rational action' (IDI_PL_1). Such places can be markets, immigration offices or centres for asylum seekers (in the latter case, to look for people after a negative decision). As a psychologist working for an NGO told us about the reception centre:

There are often situations where, for example, when the Border Guard arrives, men, I don't know, jump out of the windows and run away. [...] Such procedures prevail that the Border Guard usually arrives sometime in the morning. So it's also the case that some people [...] sleep in their clothes or, for example, they have some suitcases ready just in case. It's often like living in such constant anxiety and fear... (IDI_PL_17).

If the Border Guard identifies a person without a regular stay, it decides how to proceed further. As a lawyer from NGO stated:

You can't do all this at one time, i.e., for example, identify a person on the street because he doesn't have any papers, and then immediately give him a decision and put him on a plane on the same day. It all goes on. So this procedure usually means that either the person is set free, so to speak, or the proceedings are ongoing and he must appear to the authority, receive the decision, or appeal against it. And then, as a result of this decision, he may be obliged to return home, or he may be detained at the very beginning, at the moment of checking the legality of stay, for the duration of the procedure, when the Border Guard decides that such a person has no prospects

to the fact that he will appear before the authority and that he will simply not interrupt the procedure and will not hide (IDI_PL_8).

This means that the Border Guard may immediately, after capturing a person, apply to the court to impose detention. This, however, has to be adequately substantiated. As a former officer said:

In the application for placing a foreigner in a guarded centre, it must be demonstrated that the authority is not able to apply alternative measures to detention, because, for example, the foreigner does not have a travel document, because the foreigner does not have the financial means to live anywhere at all, or is unable to indicate a place where he could be allowed or otherwise ordered to stay. So there is, for example, a risk of escape [which] exists in particular when the foreigner, for example, crosses the border contrary to the regulations (IDI_PL_2).

Detention is, therefore, considered to be an important facilitator of forced returns. Moreover, as another Border Guard officer informed us, the behaviour of the migrants is one of the conditions upon which detention can be decided. He/she explained that the officers are concerned with being charged in case a person would commit a dangerous deed if released:

Well, if I let him go, right? He's going to commit some crime, right? Such a serious crime. Oh well, then they will hold me accountable. Why did I let him go? So, yes, I may even be criminally liable. I haven't fulfilled my obligations, have I? Verifications and so on concerning the stay of this person in Poland in terms of its threat to order and security (IDI_PL_20).

Another stage of the procedure is issuing the order of removal. According to lawyers and NGO workers, the Border Guard rarely takes into account the prerequisites for humanitarian stay and is mostly determined to issue a removal decision. As they stated, the engagement of the Commissioner for Human Rights (or for Children's Rights) is often helpful in obtaining the decision that the return is not possible due to humanitarian reasons (both institutions can monitor the actions of the Border Guard, control the spaces such as detention centres and take legal actions). Issuing a decision sometimes requires cooperation with the country of origin in terms of the identification of the person. As another Border Guard officer told us, there is a mechanism of interviews conducted in Poland by officials of a potential country of origin with a person who does not have documents, which results in issuing a travel document if a person is identified as a citizen of this country (IDI_PL_19). Moreover, as NGO workers and lawyers claimed, an understanding of the documents handed out by the Border Guard often poses problems for foreigners, which can impact their legal situation. One of the NGO lawyers explained: 'most often, the foreigner receives information about the initiation of return procedures and then immediately receives a decision, as if he had no time to present any evidence or do anything to somehow improve his situation' (IDI_PL_3). The decisions based on security issues usually have a classified substantiation (not disclosed to the person concerned), so it is extremely difficult to contest it. Also, the removal order usually contains an entry ban to the Schengen area, which is one of the reasons why some migrants prefer to stay irregularly rather than reveal their status and return voluntarily.

If the order of removal is valid (i.e., the person did not appeal¹⁶ or the second instance did not overturn the decision), the person concerned may return voluntarily within some period—except if s/he was recognised as posing a threat to security or there is a risk of absconding. If the person does not return

¹⁶ Sometimes a migrant may withdraw from his/her right to appeal, e.g., in the Podlasie Division of the Border Guard in the first half of 2023, this was the case for 272 removal orders out of 592, according to the data provided by the Division. However, according to some NGO lawyers, it is doubtful whether the migrants were fully aware of what this legal action meant in their case.

voluntarily, the Border Guard organises forced removal. However, sometimes the person may apply for international protection and this may stop the enforcement of the removal (does not apply to subsequent application). The time of removal depends on many conditions, such as:

- availability of air connections (cruise and charter),
- issues related to obtaining consent from a third country to admit a foreigner to its territory, obtaining a replacement travel document (in the case of foreigners previously subject to identification activities),
- obtaining consent to transit through the territory of another country,
- issues related to ensuring the presence of medical staff if needed,
- the operational capabilities of the unit responsible for organising return.

5.3. Materials and technologies used in the RMI connected to forced removals in Poland

The materials and technologies of RMI in Poland are constantly improving, especially after joining the EU. As a former Border Guard officer told us:

Currently, there are vehicles that are adapted to transport child seats, because you also need to be aware that the Border Guard sometimes deals with this, and these are air-conditioned vehicles. So here we can also say that the comfort of those transported is implemented in a completely different way. This IT base is also better. The Border Guard is currently able to identify people quite quickly, for example, through fingerprint readers (IDI_PL_2).

The material base for returns entails transportation and detention accommodation: prisoner buses and six detention centres. Returns are also carried out by planes, both regular and charter flights. Moreover, officers use the means of direct coercion, such as handcuffs.

The Border Guard described detention as ‘the most effective measure to guarantee the foreigner’s presence in order to carry out the return procedure’ (IDI_PL_12) effectively. According to the information obtained from the Border Guard, to optimally adapt the infrastructure and conditions in individual centres to the needs of specific groups of foreigners, the facilities have been appropriately profiled. The profile of the centre was defined according to the categories of people placed there (single men, single women, unaccompanied minors, families, including families with children). Places for people with physical disabilities have also been opened. To secure the presence of a foreigner for the purposes of the return procedure, rooms for detained persons operating within the structure of Border Guard facilities are also used. This type of infrastructure is used when the operational capabilities of the Border Guard allow the return procedure of a foreigner to be carried out within 48 hours of his/her detention. The Border Guard, under agreements between the Commanders of the Border Guard Branches and the Provincial Police Commanders, may also use rooms for detained persons remaining within the structures of Police units. NGOs and the Commissioner for Human Rights criticised conditions in detention centres. The criticism regarded, among others, the accessibility of psychological help. The material infrastructure was depicted as not proper for psychological counselling. One of the civil society counsellors told us about the conditions in which s/he was providing psychological assistance: ‘typically, these visits took place in cells where a Border Guard employee was behind the glass. There was no other possibility of meetings there’ (IDI_PL_17). Some other counsellors were not even allowed in the centres and they provided assistance through telephone.

In June 2024, one of our team members visited the detention centre in Biała Podlaska, which is a facility for up to 150 male asylum seekers or persons before a deportation operation. He met with IOM cultural assistants present in the detention centre, who were responsible for explaining the legal status of

detainees and promoting voluntary returns. The centre—as the photos present (Photo 1)—is a prison-like facility with bars in the windows and barbed wires on the top of the detention fence.

Photo 1 Photos of the detention centre in Biała Podlaska

Source: Tomasz Sieniow.

Another field visit was conducted during a forced return to Georgia in January 2024, and a Joint Return Operation, also to Georgia, was undertaken jointly with Frontex in September 2024. The photos below (Photo 2, Photo 3) present the materials used for the return. These are drawings on the wall in the room where migrants await forced removal (Georgian flag and names) and food on board during the Joint Return Operation to Georgia.

Photo 2 The room where migrants await forced removal / Photo 3 Food on board during the Joint Return Operation to Georgia

Source: Tomasz Sieniow.

Essential elements of the RMI are IT systems, which allow for the storage and obtaining of knowledge on a person's entire migration history, including administrative procedures related to his/her stay in the territory of Poland or other EU member states (POBYT system). Also, international systems such as Visa Information System (VIS), Schengen Information System (SIS), and European Asylum Dactyloscopy Database (EURODAC) are used (to contain the personal data and migration history as well as fingerprints). Moreover, the Border Guard uses national and international search systems (e.g., KSIP – Polish *Krajowy System Informacyjny Policji* – National Police Information System and Interpol) to obtain information that may affect the implementation of return procedures such as quests or criminal records. The Border Guard uses the integrated return management platform FAR (Frontex Application for Return), which allows for planning the date, return route, booking, and purchasing airline tickets for returnees, accompanying escorts and other staff (e.g., medical). As the Border Guard representatives declared:

The indicated platform [FAR] enables the exchange of information between entities involved in the return procedure regarding logistic aspects. The platform also serves to report the needs of specific EU member states regarding the organisation of joint charter flights aimed at organising the return to the country of origin of foreigners staying illegally on the territory of the EU member states (IDI_PL_12).

5.4. Relations between actors, materials, and technologies in the RMI connected to forced removals in Poland

There is significant asymmetry between the actors involved in the procedures of forced removals in Poland. First of all, our research exposed the dominant position of the Border Guard regarding forced returns. In fact, after ceding to this authority the responsibility for determining appeals in 2023, the issuing and implementing of return decisions became an internal matter of the Border Guard, and the role of other actors was reduced to a minimum. However, this does not mean that the Border Guard controls migration policy or possesses the power to determine the situation of a foreigner fully. Still, the leading institutions responsible for visa issuance are consulates, for legalisation of stay the voivodes, and for asylum procedures the Office for Foreigners. But in the case of a negative decision concerning a stay permit or asylum, the entire responsibility to determine the obligation to return, i.e., to either issue a removal order or grant a humanitarian stay, lies with the Border Guard.

Concentrating such power in the hands of the Border Guard produces some tensions between the actors involved in the migration system in Poland. Setting the Border Guard as a determining agency means that this institution—a uniformed formation—is obliged to proceed with a high bureaucratic workload. As one officer told us, according to him, the competences of decision determination should be rather concentrated in the Office for Foreigners. Furthermore, one NGO worker pointed to a waste of resources as the Border Guard, upon determination of the conditions for humanitarian stay, has to analyse the situation of applicants and the conditions in their country of origin when this is already done by the Office for Foreigners if the removal order results from a refused asylum claim. At the same time, there is insufficient staffing in the Border Guard unit responsible for proceedings of different kinds of decisions for foreigners after taking over the role of the appeal body. The situation is even more difficult because there is no complimentary role of other services, such as the Police, in this matter, which is unlikely to change. A Border Guard officer told us:

The police are not prepared. The police have a thousand other jobs, right? And let them focus on their tasks [...] and let it remain so. Really, the police are so burdened that if we give more here, it won't work. They are incapacitated at the moment (IDI_PL_20).

Also, there is no substantial support from the EU agency responsible for protecting external borders, i.e., Frontex. Different actors assessed the mandate of Frontex as insufficient because the agency is present only at border crossing points. However, there is also cooperation with Frontex in force in the case of the Joint Return Operations.

In our interviews, special attention was paid to the actors outside the EU. Cooperation with third countries issuing documents for their citizens is crucial, and as our study revealed this is an area of significant tensions with some states not willing to cooperate with the returns of their nationals. To prevent this situation, the Border Guard undertakes several actions. As its representatives explained, the institution attempts to develop contacts and cooperation with the relevant authorities of the main countries of origin of migrants in Poland, to launch some information campaigns addressed to migrants who would intend to enter Poland irregularly, and to initiate dialogue of responsible organs (such as the Ministry of Foreign Affairs) with 'third countries with a high risk of migration threats' to sign bilateral readmission agreements or 'cooperation agreements on returns' (IDI_PL_12). However, Poland has no reintegration scheme for the main return destinations, such as Georgia. Also, NGOs usually do not cooperate with parallel organisations in their countries of origin. One NGO worker explained:

Even though we had a lot of clients from places such as Chechnya or Georgia, we never had any special contacts with organisations there. If anything, it was with individual lawyers because our specificity is that, if anything, what we were most interested in was having contact with a lawyer who would help [...] with submitting some documents. But with organisations such as reintegration, I [couldn't] name a single one, we've never done it (IDI_PL_3).

The representatives of civil society organisations were, in general, critical of the Border Guards, particularly in the case of the situation on the border with Belarus. This was part of broad criticism of Poland's migration policy and its practical application carried out by various state institutions, expressed by civil society actors, which can be summarised in the words of one NGO worker:

The ignorance and lack of willingness of various state authorities to find out who the migrants are, why they are here, to understand this situation [...] the lack of a human approach, I would say, to foreigners. Such a very restrictive approach and lack of willingness to understand the individual situation of a person, as well as often, unfortunately, a lack of understanding of international or EU law in this area and the application of Polish regulations in the spirit of these regulations and principles (IDI_PL_7).

However, the Border Guard was the actor with whom the civil society organisation had the most difficult relations. Our interviewees from civil society organisations pointed to a kind of 'zeal' among the Border Guards, who focused on the effectiveness of performing forced returns, often at the expense of a profound examination of a given case. One lawyer expressed the wish that the Border Guard would not 'treat [migrants'] representatives as enemies' (IDI_PL_1). The same person explained that the difficulties stem from the routinised actions of the Border Guard:

The problem is that the Border Guard conducts itself too routinely [...] and] does not approach these matters individually, but the same activities, the same questions, always repeat themselves in these interrogations, in interviews with these foreigners (IDI_PL_1)

As mentioned above, the NGOs perceived the Border Guard as focused on effective returns at the expense of legal safeguards. One lawyer shared with us such an opinion, pointing out that even the intervention of the European Court of Human Rights was ineffective in preventing forced removal:

It can be described as a state of helplessness when [...] it is visible that the authorities are focused on quickly implementing the decision and have already made preparations for the implementation of this decision. Later, the decision itself is issued very quickly and its execution ... Well, I had a case where after such a decision was delivered to a foreigner within four hours ... [...] Of course, this was a decision made for the sake of state security. [...] It is implemented immediately, and even here, this measure in the form of an application to the European Court of Human Rights, which sometimes can respond to a request for interim measures within literally a few hours. Here, it also turned out to be ineffective because everything was carried out very quickly, and in fact, the attorney could not do anything (IDI_PL_14).

The NGOs pointed out some organisational hindrances of their activities, which produced tension with the Border Guard. The problem is a lack of financing for NGOs that assist migrants with appealing removal orders and conduct monitoring of returns. Moreover, in the decisions issued by the Border Guard, there is an instruction about appeals, with a referral to NGOs supposedly operating in this area, e.g., Caritas, instead of those really engaged in legal assistance for migrants.

At the same time, the NGOs were aware that the Border Guard was not conducting returns to several countries. As an NGO worker told us, there is a list of countries to which the returns are not executed:

We repeatedly contact the [Border Guard] Headquarters as part of access to public information, and they publish such a list. We even once asked how they create this list and they look at the process, at the degree of granting the amount of international protection to citizens of a given country (IDI_PL_3).

The significant area of tension between the NGOs and the Border Guard is detention. According to the lawyers working for the NGOs, long-term detention seems to be used as a tool to force acceptance of return (therefore, detention is not a measure used to prepare and implement return, which it should be according to the law) with insufficient identification of vulnerable groups in detention (faulty identification of unaccompanied minors and persons subjected to torture). However, civil society organisation workers noted the positive role of IOM cultural assistants in detention centres.

The NGO workers were critical of courts that decide on detention. As one lawyer told us:

Unfortunately, courts are often unaware of these migration regulations and seem to justify detention with reasons that do not exist in the situation of a specific foreigner. They extend it very automatically; they do not pay attention to the sensitivities and reasons that are the so-called negative grounds for detention ... (IDI_PL_3).

Another lawyer specialising in human rights explained:

The main problem that we see is a kind of 'automaticity' of the courts that decide to place foreigners in detention [...] This means firstly that the Border Guard requests detention in what is, in my opinion, too many cases, [and] secondly, that the courts are more inclined to accept it. This may result, in one sentence to defend the courts, simply from too much workload on judges. (IDI_PL_10)

Positive relations have been developed between the NGOs and the Commissioner for Human Rights as well as the Commissioner for Children's Rights. According to one NGO lawyer, the engagement of the above-mentioned institutions helps to safeguard the rights of migrants in the return procedures:

It seems to us that the authorities then conduct the proceedings more conscientiously. Maybe this is not only a psychological factor, because ... Because, of course, the Commissioner is not a guarantor of a positive decision, but I have the impression that always and if such an entity endowed with such social trust takes part in the proceedings, the authorities will also strive to consider this matter more carefully (IDI_PL_1).

In the case of detention, the tensions between the Border Guard and NGOs were palpable over the psychological care for detainees. The NGO representatives perceived the Border Guard as hampering access to the centres and to the provision of counselling services. It was sometimes interpreted as a part of the general policy of distrust in civil society organisations entering the detention centres. One psychologist working for an NGO told us:

There was always such an approach that an outsider was not perceived well [in a detention centre] because he did not work in the direction that the Guard was heading. There is also the issue of the fact that maybe the Border Guard did not want anyone to comment on the conditions in the centre or the relations between employees and [foreigners] staying there (IDI_PL_17).

At the same time, only some civil society organisations are entitled to monitor return operations. Significantly, the monitoring functions performed by NGOs and the costs incurred by these monitoring institutions are not financed from the state budget. This means that monitoring has a rather limited character, mostly covering the airport phase of the return operation. One such monitoring mission was held in January 2024 by a representative of the Rule of Law Institute and became the source of materials for our study. Another monitoring mission was realised during the Joint Return Operation to Georgia in September 2024, which also revealed relations between the Border Guard, Frontex, and the authorities of the country of origin in conducting such joint removals. A special charter flight started from Germany. On board, there were also members of the Georgian escorts, who wore civilian clothes and waistcoats so that they could be easily identified. It appeared that the aircraft's rear was reserved specifically for returnees admitted in Poland. After landing at Tbilisi airport, a briefing was held for the monitors and representatives of the German side. The NGOs generally assess the monitoring scheme as insufficient and a facade.

6. Georgia

6.1. Context – Georgia as a country receiving returned migrants¹⁷

Georgia is known as an emigration country due to high unemployment, poverty, and low salaries, and Georgians abroad count around 860,000 people, which is 23% of the country's population (Khishtovani et al. 2022). The main destination for Georgian migrants, as of 2017, was Russia (about 450,000), followed by Greece (about 81,000) and Ukraine (about 65,000) (SCMI 2019). Thus, remittances from migrants working abroad are significant for Georgia's economy, and in 2018, as many as 57% of Georgians abroad were sending money to their family homes.

¹⁷ This section was developed on the basis of (Krępa et al. 2024), research results from fieldwork (interviews), and desk research regarding Georgia.

Since the introduction of visa-free travel to the Schengen area for Georgian citizens in 2017, the number of asylum applications from Georgians in the EU/Schengen countries has increased. Yet, around 95% of these applications have been rejected (as of 2018), and some EU member states recognise Georgia as a safe country (SCMI 2019). At the same time, there was also an increase in the number of Georgians being refused entry to the EU/Schengen states, notably for reasons such as failing to justify their purpose and conditions of stay.

Due to the above considerations, return migration constitutes an important element of the Georgian migration landscape. The number of Georgians ordered to leave the EU increased from 6,345 in 2015 to 9,754 in 2018, and in the same period, the growth of figures regarding forced and voluntary returns was even higher—in sum, from 3,140 up to 6,625 (SCMI 2019). The number of readmission requests received by Georgia from the EU states in 2023 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Readmission requests received by Georgia from EU member states in 2023

Country	Received	Approved	Rejected
Germany	2,771	2,760	11
France	635	633	2
Greece	175	173	2
Poland	106	106	0
Italy	97	97	0
The other countries	399	394	5
Total	4,183	4,163	20

Source: Information received upon request from the Ministry of the Interior of Georgia (2024).

6.2. Georgia – return infrastructure from the perspective of the receiving country

According to Georgia’s Migration Strategy, ‘it is the country’s priority to encourage the return of Georgian citizens from abroad and facilitate their reintegration upon return’ (SCMI 2020, p. 36). The increase in returns also contributed to an increase in the number of beneficiaries of reintegration programmes, but the returnees must meet eligibility criteria, such as minimum time spent abroad. That is why the number of returnees is higher than the number of beneficiaries of reintegration programmes. For instance, in 2018, there were 815 beneficiaries of reintegration programmes in Georgia, while the number of returns was 6,625. Most reintegration beneficiaries are returnees from EU states (SCMI 2020). The most common form of reintegration assistance is an income-generating project grant (financial assistance to start a small business), while an identified shortage exists in psychological help (IOM 2021).

The core element of Georgian return infrastructure is The State Programme for Supporting Reintegration of Returned Georgian Migrants (state-funded), which offers medical services, social projects, vocational education, and temporary livelihood to Georgians irregularly residing abroad for more than one year and rejected or accepted asylum applicants. The main actors coordinating the implementation of return policies are the Ministry of the Interior and the Ministry of Labour, Health and Social Affairs. There are relevant international actors like the EU institutions (notably Frontex), the International Organisation

for Migration, and the International Centre for Migration Policy Development (ICMPD). In the practical dimension, the programmes are mostly implemented by different NGOs, mainly Georgian, but also foreign ones. The Georgian government also cooperates with the EU member states at the practical level, e.g., between the embassies/consulates and police in the EU (IDI_GE_22). In this regard, the Georgian Ministry of Foreign Affairs has also its role in the return system.

Since 2003, IOM has operated a separate EU-funded programme for those who have unlawfully stayed abroad or rejected asylum applicants (SCMI n.d. b). The programme offers consulting, temporary accommodation provision, necessary medication purchase, training and job placement, and assistance in income-generating activities (together with funding) (IOM n.d.; SCMI n.d. b). Moreover, Frontex supports Georgia in providing reintegration assistance in formal partnership with Caritas International Belgium, which cooperates with Caritas Georgia.

There are also programmes developed by sending countries, and the returnees can benefit from both the state programme and those projects. One example was the project *Strengthening the Development Potential of the EU Mobility Partnership in Georgia through Targeted Circular Migration and Diaspora Mobilization* (2013-2016), offered to 40 professionals of the nursing and hospitality sector as well as encouraging 45 Georgians trained in Germany to return home and set up enterprises (SCMI n.d. a). Another example is the French Office for Immigration and Integration (OFII) programme for Georgian returnees, which aims to assist them in starting businesses as well as includes social and medical assistance and support for professional and economic projects (OFII 2022).

The statistics on the beneficiaries of all the programmes are as follows. According to the IOM, between 2015 and 2019, there were 4,929 beneficiaries within four programmes: the programme implemented by the IOM (2,607), the Government of Georgia's State Reintegration Programme (987), the project implemented by Caritas (732), and the OFII's reintegration programme (603) (IOM 2021, p. 11).

6.3. Return infrastructure in Georgia – how does it operate in practice?

In this section, we focus on the relations between the actors and the materialities they employ that impact the effectiveness of return infrastructure in Georgia, mostly in the area of reintegration, which is the main challenge in this country's migration system. Also, the still unresolved problem of internally displaced persons from the territories occupied by Russia is a predicament for the effectiveness of the reintegration system.

Reintegration is a complex process that spans from the pre-departure phase to a long time after return, and—if it fails—can end in a re-return. As one Georgian NGO worker said, 'reintegration starts before they [the migrants] even are deported. That the first, you know, information about the opportunities in Georgia is given back' (IDI_GE_2-3-4). This is one of the most crucial findings from our research regarding Georgia—proper access to relevant information should be strengthened, especially before the formal return. Lack of information can lead to skipping reintegration opportunities, further reinforced by procedural issues. As the study conducted by the IOM revealed, the State Programme was used mainly by proactive and independent migrants due how they applied for participation (IOM 2021, p. 11). Thus, the very 'entry point' to the system seems a weak part of the return infrastructure and needs strengthening cooperation between various actors. A good practice was an information campaign depicted by one respondent, which took place in 2015 and was organised by the Georgian government, Georgian embassies, and diaspora organisations (IDI_GE_20).

In general, various overlapping programmes regarding return and reintegration implemented by different actors can be considered a factor leading to synergy, rather than an obstacle. As one of our

interviewees stated, ‘the State Migrations Reintegration Programme is simply too small. Basically, it has no impact’ (IDI_GE_8-9-10). Therefore, the programmes developed by various EU member states seem to fill the gap in the assistance provision of returnees in Georgia and attempt to cover specific needs which are not included in the other programmes. For instance, sometimes children who spent most (or all) of their life abroad need to ‘get private tutoring to enhance their Georgian language skills so that they can join their peers and not [earn] lower grades [than those that] correspond to their age because of their language problems’ (IDI_GE_8-9-10). However, again, the proper dissemination of information about various programmes seems to be an essential point. Also, some interviewees were sceptical about cooperation with the Georgian government. As one of the NGO workers stated: ‘We do not work with the government (...) because [the] government do[es] not really have any kind of programmes to support people who are returning for us to cooperate with them’ (IDI_GE_2-3-4). On the other hand, one respondent pointed out the project-based (often short-term) mode of work as very problematic (IDI_GE_20).

The importance of NGOs implementing the programmes and assisting migrants should be emphasised. The NGOs employees work closely with beneficiaries to write or correct business plans, which otherwise would be difficult to be done in an effective way because of the lack of proper know-how by returnees. One of our interviewees admitted: ‘in most cases, we change their business plan with the very close cooperation and negotiation of the beneficiary, because (...) their view about what they can do in Georgia, in Tbilisi, in Kutaisi is much different, different from what they really can do’ (IDI_GE_2-3-4).

It should be noted that there are relevant actors not officially belonging to the return infrastructure who can significantly impact the effectiveness of the reintegration of returnees. This regards especially the returnees’ families, as our respondents listed strong social links in Georgian society as an important factor facilitating reintegration. A public administration worker said that in the case of accommodation, Georgians can rely on their relatives because: ‘we are believing that if someone find[s] our relatives in the street, it’s our shame’ (IDI_GE_11), and as the recent IOM study revealed that 68% of Georgian returnees from Germany expressed strong community belonging in Georgia (IOM 2024, p. 48). On the other hand, family can deteriorate reintegration opportunities because, as our interviewees also emphasised, in public opinion, returnees may not need much help because they should possess resources achieved during migration. One interviewee depicted this attitude with the words: ‘When you come back from abroad, everyone thinks of you as rich, no one knows what you earned there, you don’t have anything there, and now you have to help everyone. Well, I think it’s also very burdensome for these people’ (IDI_GE_24). Thus, disseminating proper knowledge about the returns should ideally target the Georgian population.

6.4. Georgian system of reintegration as an extension of Poland’s RMI

The policies regarding Georgian returnees can be seen as an extension of the RMI of Poland due to the strong anchoring of returns to Georgia within the framework of the cooperation of this country with the EU. As the European Council stated in 2016, efficient returns would be essential in the case of partnership with non-EU countries (European Council 2016a; 2016b) and migration issues remain salient also under the European Neighbourhood Policy (Delcour 2013). Georgia is a part of the Eastern Partnership which is a complex cooperation scheme including *inter alia* the Panel on Migration and Asylum. The panel has functioned since 2011 with the objective to ‘strengthen the asylum and migration systems of Eastern partners and advance the dialogue on migration and asylum issues between the Eastern partners and the EU, as well as amongst the Eastern partners’ (European Commission n.d.).

Georgia has a long history of cooperation with the EU regarding returns. In 2009, a *Joint Declaration on cooperation in the framework of EU's Partnership for Mobility* was signed between Georgia and six EU member states. This initiative focuses on fighting irregular migration and the promotion of legal migration paths, with readmission and reintegration as the important components. Moreover, the EU-Georgia visa liberalisation agreement stipulates that 'visa facilitation should not lead to illegal migration' and pays 'special attention to security and readmission' (Agreement 2011a, preamble) and was signed together with the agreement on readmission (Agreement 2011b). The full implementation of the readmission agreement was stipulated in the EU-Georgia Association Agreement (2014, art. 16), and the effective returns remain an expectation from Georgia in case of the general integration process with the EU.

Cooperation with the EU significantly impacts the development of the Georgian return infrastructure. Some projects in this field are co-funded by the EU and a sending member state. According to our respondents, assisted voluntary returns are funded by the EU funds and the governments of the sending countries. Within this form of cooperation, combined flights are also organised. As one respondent noted, with EU funding and support of IOM, the Readmission Case Management Electronic System (RCMES) has been developed, which is a web-based, secure platform to facilitate information flows between partner countries and Georgia concerning requests on readmission (IDI_GE_21).

Therefore, the activities performed by Georgian authorities, regarding Georgian citizens returning from the EU, are a logical continuation of the RMI of a given member state. They have a solid basis in the form of the legal agreements between the EU and Georgia and effective reintegration of returnees is a prerequisite for efficiency of the RMI in a sending country.

7. Conclusion

Three types of returns presented in this report—assisted voluntary returns, forced removals, and pushbacks—should not be seen as strictly separate forms of border practices targeting migrants in Poland. Instead, they occupy different points on a continuum of coercion regarding the construction of return. A given person, e.g., one entering Poland irregularly from Belarus with the will to apply for international protection, may be either pushed back or issued a removal order. If the application was lodged but ended with negative decision, the person may leave voluntarily or forcibly. Thus, each form can happen to the same person and many contingent factors can impact how the return is processed. These factors concern the practices of various actors and their capabilities stemming from accessible materials. Moreover, as the practices (doings) are based in legal acts, they also vary depending on the interplay of actors engaged, their power and interests. The presented construction of return should be understood in the context of Poland's position in the global migration system.

Poland was a country of net emigration until the second decade of the 21st century. The situation changed mainly due to accelerated economic growth after the EU accession in 2004 and the outbreak of the conflict in eastern Ukraine in 2014. However, the number of asylum applications or forced returns was rather low at that time. The topic of return, as with overall migration-related issues, was not politicised before the parliamentary elections in 2015. The situation was aggravated in 2021 when Belarusian leader Alexandr Lukashenka instrumentalised migration against the EU, mostly from the Middle East and Africa, to facilitate or even force irregular border crossings to Poland, Latvia, and Lithuania. This resulted in the militarisation of the border regime and pushbacks. However, some asylum applications were allowed to be lodged, and after rejection, the need for performing returns increased considerably.

After the full-scale Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, Poland applied a legal solution based on temporary protection status, and the general policy towards people fleeing the war was rather open-door-based. However, in the case of the war's end, the question of the further stay of Ukrainian beneficiaries of temporary protection in Poland would become an essential issue regarding the return policy.

The cooperation of Georgia and the EU in terms of returns is an example of the externalisation of migration policies by the EU. It is substantially facilitated by the previous commitment of Georgians to European integration but also by the extensive network of local NGOs implementing reintegration schemes. However, despite the relevance of Georgia as a country receiving returnees from Poland, there are currently no bilateral programmes enhancing return procedures developed by Polish authorities. Therefore, Poland's membership in the EU provides this country the possibility to use the already established links between the EU institutions and Georgian state and make Georgian reintegration system an extension of Poland's return migration infrastructure. This compliments the understanding of the whole process of constructing migrants' deportability as embedded in the global hierarchies building up the relations between states' migration systems.

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